

Optimization of dry land through soybean plants with Integrated Crop Management (ICM) among palm oil plant Jambi Province

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ABSTRACT

Diversification of food crops at young oil palm trees is an effort to diversify land use, either by intercropping or rotation. Soybean can be planted in the area between young oil palm (1-3 years old). The purpose of the assessment is to look at the growth and productivity and analysis of soybean farming at young oil palm of dry land. The assessment was carried out at 2 years old of oil palm plantation in Pelayangan Village, Muara Tembesi Sub-district, Batanghari District, Jambi Province, from May to August 2016. The area of 1 ha of soybean plantation and application of technological components through integrated crop management approach (ICM). This included the use of superior varieties of Anjasmoro, Argomulyo, Dena 1 and Devon with the spacing of 30 cm x 15 cm, 2 seeds/hole, fertilizers of urea 50 kg/ha, SP 36 100 kg/ha, KCl 50 kg/ha, dolomite 1000 kg/ha and pest control. Observed parameters were soybean growth, productivity and farming analysis of several soybean varieties. The analysis used was the analysis of acceptance, opinion, and the balance of revenue on the cost (R/C). The results showed that the growth of Anjasmoro and Dena 1 varieties was better than Devon and Argomulyo varieties. Anjasmoro variety gave the highest yield of 1.08 t/ha followed by Dena 1 of 0.98 t/ha, Devon of 0.90 t/ha and Argomulyo of 0.85 t/ha. The highest revenue was Rp 2.098.000 using Anjasmoro and the lowest was Rp 438.000 using Argomulyo variety, while the revenue for Dena 1 and Devon varieties was Rp 1.370.000 and Rp 808.000, respectively. R/C ratio was 1.32 for Anjasmoro, 1.07 for Argomulyo, 1.21 for Dena 1 and 1.13 for Devon varieties. Financially, Anjasmoro variety is the most favorable variety compared to other varieties.

Keywords: Soybean, productivity, analysis of farming, intercropping

INTRODUCTION

Oil palm is one of the important plantation commodities in Indonesia, both as a foreign exchange earner and as a job opportunity. It is the main source of income for farmers and as a source of driving growth in the region. One effort to increase the productivity of oil palm in Indonesia is to do rejuvenation of old oil palm. This effort is considered to be very effective activity in increasing production, while without rejuvenation of oil palm productivity would nationally continue to decline (Herman and Pranomo, 2011). In conducting

replanting, farmers find several obstacles, namely: 1) Capital (cutting trees, nurseries, planting and maintenance), 2) The transition period occurred between nurseries and the initiation of bearing fruit where farmers do not have income, and 3) The pattern of cooperation in the development of oil palm plantations, whether through an intiplasma or self-help pattern.

Planting of food crops at young oil palm areas is an effort to diversify land use, either intercropping or intercropping and rotation. Upland rice, corn and soybeans can be planted in young oil palm areas (age 1–3 years) (Darwis and Tarigans, 1990). Understory food crops at coconuts provide several advantages and benefits, including the more efficient and productive of farming land use, the increase farm productivity, use of inputs more efficiently, and the more secure of farmers' income (Tarigans and Sumanto, 1995).

In the most important cropping business is maximizing production of cultivated plants. One way is to adjust the system or the best spacing to get optimum light. The use of 4-eye and 5-eye systems can maximize light intensity and plants can absorb nutrients well (Maryani and Gusmawartati, 2009). Sarwendah (2015) reported that immature oil palm had an empty growth space of 65 percent. The productivity of rice, corn and soybeans grown in intercropping was 315,72 kg/ha, 2.400 kg/ha and 640 kg/ha.

The existence of intercrops among the rows of oil palm plantations TBM 3 does not disturb the growth of oil palm. Planting of intercrops does not affect the growth of young oil palm plants as the main crop, even economically can increase profits with the B/C ratio between 1.30-2.05 (Purba et al., 1998). Another advantage of the concept of oil palm-based intercropping system is to support the sustainability of agricultural businesses through maximizing land use, yield stability and profitability (Erhabor and Filson, 1999).

Therefore, this study needs to be done to optimize the area use between young oil palm plants for food crops before the oil palm begin to produce fruits. The purpose of the study is to assess the growth, productivity and the analysis of soybean farming among oil palm crops on dry land.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out in the area of young oil palm of 2 year old in Pelayangan Village, Muara Tembesi district, Batanghari regency, Jambi Province from May to August 2016. The soybean varieties used were Anjasmoro, Argomulyo, Dena 1 and Devon with a planting area of 1 ha. The applied technology to increase productivity of soybean farming with integrated crop management (ICM) approach was land clearing, and the eradication of coconut beetle larvae, soil tillage, soybean cultivation, the use of labelled seeds, superior varieties, planting distance of 30x15 cm, fertilizer dosage of 50 kg urea /ha, 100 kg SP 36/ha, 50 kg KCl/ha and 1000 kg dolomite/ha. Amount of seed was 40

kg/ha and planted 2 seeds/hole, weed control 2 times and adjusted weed conditions in the field. Making/repairing drainage system to regulate the water so that there would be no flooding. Regular spacing to facilitate fertilization, weed and pest control. Fertilization was carried out at 5-7 cm from the plant and it was covered with soil and soybean planting hole was covered with a mixture of manure and dolomite. Pest control was carried out with an integrated pest control. Parameters observed were plant performance, plant height, number of branches, number of filled pods, number of empty pods, age of harvest and yield. Growth and yield data were processed and tabulated while the economic analysis included revenue, income and profits, R/C ratio (Swastika, 2004 and Malian, 2004).

1. Analysis of farming income:

Where :

- Π = Net farm income (Rp/ha)
- Y = Total production (kg/ha)
- P_y = Price of selling soybeans (Rp/kg)
- X_i = Farm input level (Rp/ha)
- P_{xi} = Farm input price (Rp/kg)
- BL = Other costs (Rp/ha)

2. Farm feasibility (R/C)

Where :

- R/C = Revenue and cost ratio
- NPT = Total production value (Rp/ha)
- BT = Value of total cost (Rp/ha)

Under the condition :

- $R/C > 1$, farming is economically profitable
- $R/C = 1$, economic farming is at a break-even point (BEP)
- $R/C < 1$, economic farming is not profitable (loss)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Plant Growth

Plant growth of all varieties showed high growth percentage, it was suspected that all varieties had good adaptation, good seed quality and supported by growing environmental conditions (Table 1). The average percentage of plant growth for all varieties was 80-90%. The high percentage of growth was attributed by good quality seeds, the availability of nutrients in the soil deriving from addition of dolomite and organic fertilizer. The performance of soybean plants showed quite diverse growth according to the characteristics of each variety (Table 1). At the beginning of planting soybean growth showed good performance for all varieties, but few weeks later soybean growth

was hampered by very low rainfall. At the vegetative phase and the early generative phase of sufficient rainfall and visible growth of soybean plants each variety was affected by the availability of water.

Table 1. Average percentage of growth, performance, plant height, and branches number of several soybean varieties at young oil palm areas

No	Varieties	Growth percentage (%)	Crop performance	Plant height (cm)	Number of branches
1.	Anjasmoro	80-90	3	55,4	2,2
2.	Argomulyo	80-90	3-5	41,0	1,6
3.	Dena 1	80-90	3	45,2	2,0
4.	Devon	80-90	3-5	39,6	1,8

Of the four varieties tested, the growth of Anjasmoro and Dena 1 varieties was better than Devon and Argomulyo varieties. This shows that Anjasmoro and Dena 1 varieties are quite drought resistant compared to the other two varieties. Pests that appear in soybean plantations are leaf rollers, green ladybugs and grasshoppers while the disease is like leaf rust. Of the four varieties tested, the response was quite resistant to pests and diseases. The variety of plant performance and reactions to pests/diseases are strongly influenced by genetic characteristics and characteristics of varieties and environmental factors. According to Satoto and Suprihatno (1998), the phenotic appearance of plants is a reflection of genetic and environmental influences during plant development, it would be able to change the stability of the nature of a plant variety. Las *et al.* (1993) said that environmental physical factors such as soil and climate predominantly affect plant growth in the field. From the test results, it could be seen that Anjasmoro and Dena 1 varieties have higher plant growth than other varieties. High growth of soybean plants is optimal even though the initial growth phase is inhibited. This is presumably the genotypic ability of each variety and due to the application of dolomite and organic fertilizer that increase soil pH and nutrient availability for plants. The number of branches of Anjasmoro variety followed by varieties of Dena 1, Devon and Argomulyo.

According to Baharsyah *et al.*, (1993) the length of day, temperature and interaction of temperature and day length are the main factors that influence soybean flowering. Flowering occurs because there are pigments that are responsive to light stimulation. In addition to affecting flowering, the duration of irradiation also affects the number of fertile books, plant height, flowering period, period from flowering to pod formation, and pod growth to maturation. A long day would extend the period of each phase of vegetative and

generative development and increase the number of fertile books and plant height.

Growth and yield Components

The average age of soybean harvest depends on each variety. The soybean harvesting age ranged from 77,00to 85,00 DAP. ForAnjasmoro variety, the harvest age is longer than other soybean varieties and Dena 1 variety has a faster harvesting age.

Table 2. Average harvest age, number of filled and empty pods andyield of several soybean varieties at young oil palm areas

No	Varieties	Age ofharvest (days)	Number of pods	The number of empty pods	Result (t/ha)
1.	Anjasmoro	85,00	32,00	5,00	1,08
2.	Argomulyo	80,00	25,00	11,00	0,85
3.	Dena 1	77,00	30,00	10,00	0,98
4.	Devon	83,00	28,00	8,00	0,90

The results of the study showed that the number of pods andempty pods varied between varieties.The highest number of filled pods were found for Anjasmoro varietyand the lowest for Argomulyo variety,while the lowest number of empty pods was Anjasmoro varietyand the highest was Argomulyo varieties.This is caused by environmental factorsin addition to genetic factors. The results of soybean dry seeds per hectare showed differences between varieties.Of the four soybean varieties tested, Anjasmoro varieties gave the highest yield of 1,08 t/ha followed by Dena 1 variety of 0,98 t/ha. The lowest yield wasArgomulyo variety of 0,85 t/ha. From the results of research on acid dry land in Langkat North Sumatra, the Anjasmoro variety production was higher than Kaba and Sinabung varieties which were 2,03 t/ha (Amrizal, *et al.* 2004).

Economic Analysis of Soybean Farming

To measure the rate of return on soybean farming costs, the revenue ratio of the input costs used forcalculation, while farm income is the difference between the yield value and production costs. The income and farm income from the four varieties are different (Table 3).The highest revenue was obtained for Anjasmoro variety namelyRp. 8.640.000 followed by the Dena 1 variety which was Rp. 7.840.000, while the Argomulyo and Devon varieties were Rp. 6.800.000 and Rp. 7.200.000, respectively. The highest income was Rp. 2,098,000 (Anjasmoro) and the lowest income was Argomulyo variety which was Rp

438.000, while the Dena 1 and Devon varieties were Rp. 1.370,000 and Rp 808,000. The low income obtained from Argomulyo and Devon varieties was due to lower yields compared to Anjasmoro and Dena 1 varieties. The R/C ratio of each variety was 1,32 (Anjasmoro), 1,07 (Argomulyo), 1,21 (Dena 1) and 1,13 (Devon). This shows that soybean farming of four varieties provides benefits. However, the R/C ratio for Anjasmoro and Dena 1 varieties is better than the R/C ratio for Argomulyo and Devon varieties. Thus financially, the Anjasmoro soybean variety is a new superior variety that is most profitable compared to other varieties.

Table 3. Economic analysis of several soybean varieties per hectare planted at young oil palm areas

Description	Anjasmoro	Argomulyo	Dena 1	Devon
INPUT (Rp)				
Production Facilities				
- Seed	400.000	400.000	400.000	400.000
- Dolomite	1.000.000	1.000.000	1.000.000	1.000.000
- Urea	130.000	130.000	130.000	130.000
- SP 36	260.000	260.000	260.000	260.000
- KCl	400.000	400.000	400.000	400.000
- Round up	400.000	400.000	400.000	400.000
- DMA	112.000	112.000	112.000	112.000
- Reagent	250.000	250.000	250.000	250.000
Amount	2.952.000	2.952.000	2.952.000	2.952.000
Labor				
- Spray grass	280.000	280.000	280.000	280.000
- Plant	2.000.000	2.000.000	2.000.000	2.000.000
- Fertilization	150.000	150.000	150.000	150.000
- Weeding	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000
- Pest control	300.000	300.000	300.000	300.000
- Harvest / Processing	660.000	480.000	588.000	510.000
Amount	3.590.000	3.410.000	3.518.000	3.440.000
Total	6.542.000	6.362.000	6.470.000	6.392.000
OUTPUT				
- Results (kg)	1.080	850	980	900
- Price (Rp)	8.000	8.000	8.000	8.000
- Receipt (Rp)	8.640.000	6.800.000	7.840.000	7.200.000
- Income (Rp)	2.098.000	438.000	1.370.000	808.000
- R/C	1,32	1,07	1,21	1,13

CONCLUSION

Soybean that adaptive and has high yield planted at young oil palm areas is Anjasmoro (1,08 t/ha) that gave the income of Rp. 2.098.000 with R/C ratio of 1,32.

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